

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

¹Sh.A.Abdujalilova, ²Z.Karimova

¹D.p.s., associate professor ChSPU

²Master's student of ChSPU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7876442>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the problem of introducing innovative technologies in the activities of teachers of preschool institutions for children with disabilities.*

Keywords: *art therapy, music therapy, puppet therapy, mnemonics, creative game therapy, laughter therapy, body-oriented technique.*

The education of children with developmental disabilities provides for the creation of a special correctional and developmental environment, rehabilitation, training, upbringing, and social adaptation conditions for them. Many preschool children with developmental disabilities have problems with cognitive processes and mental activity; physical development and sensory function disorders of various degrees; as well as rapid fatigue, distraction and hyperactivity. In order to ensure the full development of children with developmental disabilities, it is important to introduce non-traditional approaches, individual programs, and innovative technologies to the field of preschool education. In relation to the pedagogical process, the word innovation is used to implement a new form, purpose, content and methods in the organization of interaction between the pedagogue and children with developmental disabilities. Active use of innovative technologies is the main criterion for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Authors of innovative technologies are V.V. Konovalenko, T.A. Tkachenko, T.B. Filicheva, S.V. Konovalenko, L.N. Smirnova, N.V. Nisheva. The main function of innovations is to change the components of the pedagogical process: purpose, content, form, method, teaching and training tools. Education of children with special needs implies the creation of a special correctional and developmental environment that provides favorable conditions for them, creates equal opportunities for studying with healthy children within the framework of special educational standards. One of the conditions for the proper organization of the educational process in a multidisciplinary specialized pre-school education organization is to know the structure of the defect and to understand that it is possible to correct deviations in the development of the so-called primary defect. Health technologies for children with special needs are quite relevant. The purpose of these technologies is to create an opportunity to maintain the health of children with special needs, to create knowledge and skills in a child to lead a healthy lifestyle, and to teach him to use the acquired social experience in everyday life. The use of art therapy, information and communication technologies by innovative technologists in the preschool education system is also relevant.

Art therapy in a preschool educational organization is a path to a child's mental health. There are the following types of art therapy: music therapy (vocal therapy, playing instruments), fairy-tale therapy, isotherapy, mnemonics, doll therapy, creative play therapy, aromatherapy,

laughter therapy, chromotherapy (treatment with light and color), kinesiotherapy (dance therapy, logarithmics, psychogymnastics).

Music therapy is a method of psychotherapy based on the emotional perception of music based on its tone, rhythmic basis and performance. Music can have a positive effect on the emotional development of children with special needs, helps to build mutual trust and understanding between the participants of the educational process. In particular, when the elements of Karl Orff's "Music for Children" methodology are used in correctional work with children with special needs, the musical talent of children is revealed through improvisation in music and movement. In this, it is not important that children perform some rare work, but the creative process that allows them to express themselves. Improvisations in art classes are performed as a team. It is this feature that allows every child to find his place, regardless of his disability and level of musical ability.

Isotherapeutic techniques (unconventional painting) "pressing", finger painting, painting with soft paper, painting on the surface of glass, painting with semolina, leaves, cotton, sticks, stone painting technique, lid dipping painting, palm painting are used for the cognitive development of children with special needs.

Fairytale therapy is a technique that uses the form of a fairy tale to develop a person, expand thinking, and improve interaction with the environment through speech.

Doll therapy is considered a branch of art therapy, in which a doll is used as the main method of influence, as an intermediate object of interaction between a child and an adult.

Mnemonics is a system of techniques that facilitate recall and expand memory by creating artificial associations. The essence of mnemonics is that symbols are created for each word or phrase, and the text is represented in a complete drawing. By using these drawings, the child can easily recite a poem or text.

Creative play therapy is a method that helps to improve speech and develop imagination, as well as the emotional-volitional sphere. Sand therapy helps children with special needs to improve practical communication skills, enrich vocabulary, develop connected speech, fine motor skills, activity and concentration, expand imagination and figurative thinking.

Laughter therapy is a type of psychotherapy that helps relieve pain, relieve emotional stress, relax, and overcome shyness. Humor and laughter raise the mood, help to be open to communication, and to be able to withstand stressful situations.

Aromatherapy is the use of essential oils and oil suspensions to promote health. Phrases help manage mood, calm the nervous system, increase productivity and maintain a good mood. There are different types of aromatherapy, such as taking an aromatherapy bath, scenting a room, and massaging with aromatic oils.

Chromotherapy (color therapy) - restoring the individual biological rhythm of children with special needs using a specially selected color. Preschool age is a period of intensive emotional development of a child. Stimulating the intellectual and emotional development of children with special needs using color therapy is a well-founded and effective method. Color therapy undoubtedly helps to improve the environment in the children's community, to stimulate the intellectual development of children with special needs, and to acquire the skills of psychophysical relaxation.

Information technologies of education are pedagogical technologies used in information. Modern information technology is based on psychological-pedagogical and methodological rules

developed by L.S.Vygotsky, V.Y.Davidov, P.Y.Galperin, A.R.Luria, A.B.Zaporoghes, A.N.Leontev, D.B.Elkonin. The use of ICT in working with children with special needs increases their motivation in organizing their cognitive activities; due to the increase in emotional tone, it allows to create a didactic manual in a short time, which allows the curriculum to remain in the long-term memory of preschool children of this category.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that innovative technologies in the activity of pedagogues in working with children with special needs of preschool age are becoming a promising tool for correctional work. Comprehensive support, among innovative methods, without requiring special effort, contributes to the optimization of the correction process of disabled children, improves the whole organism, creates great opportunities for the formation of communication skills and general development, increases the ability of children to accept and master new knowledge, which in turn contributes to their successful socialization.

REFERENCES

1. Akatov L.I. Sotsialnaya reabilitatsiya detey s ogranichennimi vozmojnostyami zdorovya. Psixologicheskiye osnovi / L.I.Akato. – M.: Vlados.2003 – 225 s.
2. Andersen B. Multimedia v obrazovanii / B.Andersen, V.B.Briik. Moskva: Drofa 2007 – 213 s
3. Gnezdilova O.N. Psixologicheskiye aspekty innovatsionnoy deyatel'nosti pedagoga / / Psixologicheskaya nauka i obrazovaniye. - 2006 god. - №4. - 61- 65 s.
4. Zemlyachenko M. V. Ispolzovaniye logopedom innovatsionnykh tekhnologiy v rabote s doshkolnikami s ogranichennymi vozmojnostyami zdorovya [tekst] // innovatsionnyye pedagogicheskiye tekhnologii: materialy VII Mejdunarodnoy konferentsii. nauka. Konf. (Kazan, Oktyabr 2017 Goda). - Kazan: Buk,2017. - 69-71 S.-URL <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/271/13028/> (дата обращения: 26.03.2020).
5. Kalachikova O. N. Issledovaniye sodержaniya i etapov vxojdeniya pedagogov v innovatsionnyuyu deyatel'nost // Vestnik Tomskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. - 2008 god. - №316. - 174-177s.
6. Razina N.A. professionalno-lichnostnoye razvitiye pedagoga v usloviyakh innovatsionnoy deyatel'nosti obrazovatel'nogo uchrejdeniya // sovremennyye naukoemkiye tekhnologii. - 2008 god. - №1. - 14 s.